

Coleoptera General background

- [p.1](#) 1 Protocoleoptera, figure of Moravocoleidae_02
- [p.2](#) 1 Protocoleoptera, Permian fossil, Moravocoleidae_01
- [p.3](#) 1 Protocoleoptera, Moravocoleus permianus figure & fossil
- [p.4](#) 1a Protocoleoptera, Moravocoleidae and Ademosynidae compared 117
- [p.5](#) 1b Protocoleoptera, elytral veination
- [p.6](#) 2 Fossil Coleoptera, Schizophoridae, late-middle Permian_01
- [p.7](#) 3 Fossil Coleoptera, Taldycupedidae or Asiocoleidae, middle late Permian HW base_02
- [p.8](#) Coleoptera generalized hind wing with major landmarksl_01_02
- [p.9](#) Coleoptera wing folding
- [p.10](#) Coleoptera_Intro_03 Elytron dorsal, Passalidae, Popilius disjunctus
- [p.11](#) Coleoptera_Intro_04 Elytron ventral, Passalidae, Popilius disjunctus
- [p.12](#) Coleoptera, Generalized 2 Adephaga and Myxophaga hind wing diagram with major landmarks_06
- [p.13](#) Coleoptera, Generalized 3 Adephaga and Myxophaga hind wing diagram with major landmarks_04
- [p.14](#) Coleoptera, Generalized 4 Polyphaga and Archostemata hind wing diagram with major landmarks_05
- [p.15](#) Coleoptera, Generalized 5 Polyphaga and Archostemata hind wing diagram with major landmarks_05
- [p.16](#) Coleoptera, Generalized 6, comparison of end of media in HW in suborders
- [p.17](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_01 Vein_Crossing_in_Wing_Folding_01_Suborders_Compared
- [p.18](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Adephaga, Carabidae, Calosoma sp._20
- [p.19](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Adephaga, Gyrinidae, Macrogyrus_03
- [p.20](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Archostemata, Cupedidae, Disticupes sp._01
- [p.21](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Archostemata, Cupedidae, Disticupes varians_21
- [p.22](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Archostemata, Cupedidae, Disticupes varians detail_02
- [p.23](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Artematopidae, Artematopus sp._16
- [p.24](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Artematopidae, Artematopus sp._22
- [p.25](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Artematopidae, Artematopus sp_detail_04_02
- [p.26](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Bostrichidae, Bostrichopsis sp._06
- [p.27](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Bostrichidae, Bostrichopsis sp._17
- [p.28](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Byrrhidae, Byrrhus sp._18
- [p.29](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Byrrhidae, Byrrhus sp_detail_05
- [p.30](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Cerambycidae, Eurynassa sp._07_02
- [p.31](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Cyrinidae, Macrogyrus_11
- [p.32](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dascillidae, Notodascillus sp_detail_08
- [p.33](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dascillidae, Notodascillus sp._19
- [p.34](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dermestidae, Anthrenus sp._14
- [p.35](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dermestidae, Anthrenus sp_detail_09
- [p.36](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dermestidae, Dermestes ater_15
- [p.37](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dermestidae, Dermestes maculatus_02
- [p.38](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Dermestidae, Dermestes maculatus_10_02
- [p.39](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Elateridae, Pseudotetralobus sp_detail_11
- [p.40](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Elateridae, Pseudotetralobus sp._13
- [p.41](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Eucinetidae, Eucinetus infumatus_12
- [p.42](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Eucinetidae, Eucinetus sp_detail_12
- [p.43](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Hydrophilidae, Hydrophilus sp._10
- [p.44](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Lucanidae, Lamprima_09
- [p.45](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Nosodendridae, Nosodendron unicolor_04
- [p.46](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Nosodendridae, Nosodendron unicolor_13
- [p.47](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Psephenidae, Sclerocyphon sp._15
- [p.48](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Psephenidae, Sclerocyphon sp._05
- [p.49](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Ptilodactylidae, Byrrhocrptis variegatus_14_02
- [p.50](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Rhinorhipidae, Rhinorhipus sp._16
- [p.51](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Rhinorhipus tamborensis_06
- [p.52](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Scirtidae, Pseudomicrocara sp_detail_17_02
- [p.53](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Scirtidae, Pseudomicrocara sp._07
- [p.54](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Staphylinidae, Creophilus sp._08
- [p.55](#) Vein_Crossing_and_Wing_Folding_Polyphaga, Trogossitidae, Lepidopteryx monilia_03

Protocoleoptera: Moravocoleidae Fore Wing Diagram

Moravocleus permianus: Cumulative Fig. (holotype: 1/1968, 3/1968, 6/1968, 11/1968)

Lower Permian, Obora, Moravia, the oldest known beetle

Permian fossil beetle, Moravocoleidae, *Moravocoleus permianus*

Tshekardocoleidae

The high quality preservation of Obora fossil insects.

Obora insects fossilized in fine clay that never completely lithified and that experienced some later distorting pressures. Note the difference in the length and width of the plesiomorphic elytra above. The clay sometimes preserved an insect's exoskeletal chitin layer, especially in wings, legs, and genitalia. The holotype above bears a short, sharply triangular OUTER OVIPOSITOR, which is weakly outlined between the hind wings in the above photograph. This was originally covered by a dark brown, beautifully preserved genital exoskeleton, as in a reconstruction in my 1993c: 221 paper with J. F. Lawrence. An external ovipositor is also shown in related Tshekardocoleidae (after Ponomarenko) in my 1991:177 paper. Drying of the clay in the *Moravocoleus* specimen above, after it was collected, caused the external ovipositor exoskeletal material to flake-off as I was studying it with a strong light, and this left behind only the general outline and insides of the ovipositor. A closely fitting elytra and inner ovipositor evolved in Coleoptera later. *Moravocoleus* had elytra loosely articulated with the mesonotum and an abdomen plus ovipositor shorter than the elytra. An outer ovipositor in the oldest coleopteroid insects is to be expected (not improbable, as speculated by some).

B
Fig.18

Protocoleoptera: Moravocoleidae: *Moravocoleus permianus* Lower Permian, Czech Republic

The oldest fossil beetle. Elytra of Protocoleoptera contain a locking posterior wing margin, present also in the tegmina of fossil earwigs (Blattoneoptera). Four veinal sectors (ScA, RP, MA, CuP) are reduced. Anal area bears broadened field basally between AA1+2 and AA3+4, as in Neuroptera and some Megaloptera. Unlike in Coleoptera (Fig. 36), AA3+4 is the strongest anterior anal vein.

Coleoptera: Ademosynidae: *Ademosyne speciosa* Middle Triassic, South Africa

Early fossil beetles (Coleoptera) bore on the prothorax narrow wing lobes secondarily fused to the tergum, like almost all other Neoptera and Paleoptera. Unlike in Protocoleoptera, AA1+2 is the strongest anterior anal vein. Within Endoneoptera, the veinal pattern is closest to Neuroptera and some Megaloptera, which groups share a long ScP, arculus, long MP, and long CuA.

Protocoleoptera: Moravocoleidae: *Moravocoleus permianus* Lower Permian, Czech Republic

The oldest fossil beetle. Elytra of Protocoleoptera contain a locking posterior wing margin, present also in the tegmina of fossil earwigs (Blattoneoptera). Four venal sectors (ScA, RP, MA, CuP) are reduced. Anal area bears broadened field basally between AA1+2 and AA3+4, as in Neuroptera and some Megaloptera. Unlike in Coleoptera (Fig. 36), AA3+4 is the strongest anterior anal vein.

Coleoptera: Ademosynidae: *Ademosyne speciosa* Middle Triassic, South Africa

Early fossil beetles (Coleoptera) bore on the prothorax narrow wing lobes secondarily fused to the tergum, like almost all other Neoptera and Paleoptera. Unlike in Protocoleoptera, AA1+2 is the strongest anterior anal vein. Within Endoneoptera, the venal pattern is closest to Neuroptera and some Megaloptera, which groups share a long ScP, arcus, long MP, and long CuA.

Fossil coleopteran; Schizophoridae?

late middle Permian, Isady, northern European Russia, PIN 3840/2027

Some cross veins are left out. New interpretation based on photograph and figure in Fedorenko and Pomonarenko, 2012, Paleontological Journal 46: 164-170.

The ancestral pattern indicates the identity of modern, very confusing veins.

Fossil coleopteran; Taldycupedidae or Asiocoleidae

late middle Permian, Isady, northern European Russia, PIN 3840/2042

Venation based on a figure and a photograph in Fedorenko and Pomonarenko, 2012, Paleontological Journal, 46: 164-170.

Note: CuP and claval line reduced; wing flexing folds were left out of original figure; all crossveins were probably not figured.

Fossil close to *Tetraphalerus wagneri*

Hind wing diagram

Diagram of an hypothetical beetle hind wing showing all of the major landmarks, including major folds and the central and apical folding areas.

NOSODENDRON

Extended wing

Folded wing

POLYPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

ADEPHAGA

MYXOPHAGA

POLYPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

ADEPHAGA

MYXOPHAGA

Wing folding in Coleoptera

Note that during wing folding the medial loop is placed on top of radial loop.

Note that CuP and claval line are reduced in almost all modern beetles and CuA is anchored on the AA3 vein.

Coleo: Passalidae: *Popilius disjunctus*

Coleo: Passalidae *Popilius disjunctus*

ADEPHAGA

MYXOPHAGA

ADEPHAGA

MYXOPHAGA

POLYPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

POLYPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

POLYPHAGA

ADEPHAGA
MYXOPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

POLYPHAGA

ADEPHAGA
MYXOPHAGA

ARCHOSTEMATA

Carabidae: *Calosoma*

ADEPHAGA
MACROGYRUS

Cupedidae: *Disticipes*

length: 13mm

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Cupedidae retained CuP which most beetles lost

Cupedidae: *Disticupes varians*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

ARCHOSTEMATA

Cupedidae: *Disticipes varians*

Presence of break hinges in both radial & medial loop

Artematopidae: *Artematopus*

Artematopidae: *Artematopus*

POLYPHAGA

Artematopidae: *Artematopus*

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis*

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Byrrhidae: *Byrrhus*

Byrrhidae: *Byrrhus*

Cerambycidae: *Eurynassa*

Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Dascillidae: *Notodascillus*

Dascillidae: *Notodascillus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Dermestidae: *Anthrenus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Dermestidae: *Anthrenus*

Dermeestidae: *Dermeestes ater*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Dermestidae: *Dermestes maculatus*

In hind wings, HP (humeral plate) shows its plesiomorphic composition from fulcalare PC & C, and basivenale PC & C

Dermestidae: *Dermestes maculatus*

Elateridae: *Pseudotetralobus*

Elateridae: *Pseudotetralobus*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus infumatus*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus*

Hydrophilidae: *Hydrophilus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Lucanidae: *Lamprima*

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolor*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolour*

Psephenidae: *Sclerocyplon*

Psephenidae: *Sclerocyphon*

Ptilodactylidae: *Byrrrocryptis variegatus*

Rhinorhipidae: *Rhinorhipus*

Rhinorhipidae: *Rhinorhipus tamboriensis*

Scirtidae: *Pseudomicrocara*

Scirtidae: *Pseudomicrocara*

Note presence of rarely retained CuP in very short claval line.

Staphylinidae: *Creophilus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Trogossitidae:
Lepidopteryx monilia

DORSAL

VENTRAL